

DETECTION OF DELAMINATION IN CFRP LAMINATES BY INTEGRATED FIBER-OPTIC STRAIN DISTRIBUTION SENSORS

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Keywords: NDT, Rayleigh scattering, Detection of delamination, CFRP laminates, Distributed strain sensing

ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) offers excellent properties such as low weight and high strength, but internal delamination caused by impact or fatigue is difficult to detect. To address this, we explored the use of Rayleigh scattering-based optical fiber sensors that measure surface strain distributions via Rayleigh scattering to detect delamination in real time. A CFRP laminate was prepared with artificial delamination of 35 mm or 55 mm in length at two depths: the 10th layer (1.0 mm from the surface) and the 50th layer (3.5 mm deep). Three-point bending tests were conducted, and strain distributions were measured using a distributed fiber-optic sensor. Finite element analysis (FEM) was also performed to verify the experimental results. The strain profiles from both the test and simulation showed good agreement. At the delamination tip, the strain curve exhibited a valley for shallow delamination and a peak for deeper ones. FEM results revealed that the shape and magnitude of the surface strain anomaly are sensitive to delamination depth, especially when the delamination is near the sensing surface. When the sensor was on the tensile side, characteristic strain valleys and peaks were observed around the delamination tip, varying with depth. On the compressive side, the effect was less pronounced unless the delamination was close to the surface. These findings suggest that depth estimation is possible by placing sensors on both sides of the laminate.

1 INTRODUCTION

CFRP laminated plates, known for their light weight, high strength, and high rigidity, are widely used in aircraft and other applications due to their ability to be integrally molded with stringers. However, interlaminar delamination caused by impact or fatigue is difficult to detect visually. Therefore, non-destructive testing (NDT) methods are essential for ensuring safety during regular inspections.

Conventional NDT techniques such as ultrasonic testing, X-ray inspection, and infrared thermography have been introduced and play an important role in aircraft maintenance. However, these methods require halting operations and are limited in scanning range, resulting in prolonged inspection times and increased operational costs. To reduce downtime and improve reliability, real-time structural health monitoring (SHM) is gaining attention [1].

Real-time SHM involves embedding sensor systems directly into the structure and monitoring during operation. If wide-area measurements can be achieved using a minimal number of sensors and a compact measurement system, SHM of large-scale structures—such as aircraft—could become feasible even in-flight.

Various sensor systems have been studied, including micro piezoelectric elements and electrical resistance-based sensors. Among these, distributed optical fiber sensors are particularly well-suited for detecting delamination between stringers and skins, as they can monitor strain over long distances using a single fiber. However, the commonly used Optical Time Domain Reflectometry (OTDR)

technique, while cost-effective, has limited spatial resolution (on the order of sub-meters) and is inadequate for detecting delamination at the centimeter scale required for aircraft structures.

Therefore, we focus on a Rayleigh scattering-based distributed optical fiber sensor using Optical Frequency Domain Reflectometry (OFDR), which offers spatial resolution on the order of millimeters. By measuring strain and temperature distributions, it becomes possible to detect damage more precisely [2]. Our previous work demonstrated that delamination tips could be identified at the millimeter level by analyzing surface strain distributions measured at 1 mm intervals. In particular, Mode I and Mode II delamination tips were detected by observing peaks in the strain profiles. However, the influence of delamination depth and specimen thickness on this detection method has not been fully explored.

In this study, we conducted three-point bending tests and finite element analysis (FEA) to investigate how the depth and thickness of delamination affect surface strain distributions, aiming to clarify the detection limits and improve reliability in practical SHM applications.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

3.1 Rayleigh scattering distribution sensor

A Rayleigh scattering-based distributed sensor measures the backscattered light along the length of an optical fiber and detects local strain changes using the cross-correlation method on the spatial frequency distribution of the scattered signal. Rayleigh scattering originates from refractive index mismatches at the core-cladding interface and reflects geometrical changes in the fiber. Unlike Brillouin scattering, Rayleigh scattering does not involve a frequency shift proportional to strain. However, OFDR (Optical Frequency Domain Reflectometry) provides extremely high spatial resolution, allowing hundreds of data points per millimeter. The resulting frequency spectrum shifts toward lower frequencies when the fiber is stretched. By performing cross-correlation with a reference spectrum, the amount of frequency shift can be quantified and converted to strain. In this study, the spatial interval over which the spectrum is analyzed is defined as the gauge length, which can be adjusted post-measurement.

Strain distributions were measured using a Rayleigh scattering-type distributed optical fiber sensor (ODiSI A-50, LUNA Technologies). The system supports measurement ranges from 1 to 50 meters, with a minimum spatial resolution (pitch) of 1 mm, a strain measurement range of $\pm 10,000 \mu\epsilon$, resolution of $1 \mu\epsilon$, and a sampling rate of up to 5 Hz, allowing simultaneous acquisition of strain and temperature distributions.

3.2 Experimental method

In this study, unidirectional CFRP specimens were fabricated using 60 plies of CFRP prepreg (TR350C100S, Mitsubishi Chemical) through hot press molding. To introduce delamination, a 0.1 mm thick Teflon sheet was placed between the 50th and 51st plies. Specimens with delamination lengths of 35 mm, 45 mm, and 55 mm were prepared by varying the length of the Teflon insert.

A three-point bending static test was conducted with a support span of 100 mm and a displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min (Figure 2). A fiber optic sensor was bonded to the bottom surface using instant adhesive (Figure 3). Additionally, the specimens were tested in both upright and inverted orientations, positioning the delamination at either 10 or 50 plies from the measurement surface. The load was paused at a predetermined value, and strain distributions were recorded during the test. Strain analysis was performed with a 1 mm measurement pitch and a 10 mm gauge length.

3.3 Analysis method

Finite element analysis was conducted using Abaqus with a two-dimensional model of the three-point bending test. The material properties were longitudinal Young's modulus $E_L=137\text{GPa}$, transverse modulus $E_T=9.76\text{GPa}$, shear modulus, $G_{LT}=5.17\text{GPa}$, Poisson's ratio $\nu_{LT}=0.32$. While the experiments focused on delamination at two depths (10 and 50 plies), the simulation covered a broader range of delamination depths. To evaluate the influence of plate thickness, simulations were also performed using a 9 mm thick model—twice the experimental specimen thickness.

Figure 1: CFRP specimen with artificial delamination

Figure 2: 3-point bending test

Figure 3: Location of optical fiber sensor

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Detection of position of delamination tip

Figures (a)–(c) show the strain distributions obtained from the optical fiber sensor, along with the corresponding finite element analysis (FEA) results under the same load, for specimens with delamination lengths of 35 mm, 45 mm, and 55 mm, respectively. The horizontal axis represents the distance from the specimen edge, and the numbers 10 and 50 indicate the delamination depths from the sensor surface, expressed as ply numbers.

Figure 4: Measured and FEM-calculated strain distribution at 3-point bending tests.

As shown, the experimental and FEA results show good agreement across all delamination lengths, confirming that the Rayleigh scattering-based distributed sensor provides highly accurate and spatially resolved strain measurements.

In all cases, a consistent relationship was observed between the surface strain distribution and the delamination front: a peak appeared 1 mm to the left of the delamination tip, and a sharp valley was observed 1 mm to the right when the delamination was close to the sensor surface. Notably, at a delamination length of 55 mm, the maximum global strain was located near the delamination tip rather than at the loading point

3.2 Effect of depth-wise position of delamination

The measurement surfaces were set as the upper and lower surfaces, and FEM analysis was performed by changing the delamination position. Figure 5 shows the strain distribution when the measurement surface was set as the lower surface, for delamination lengths of 35 mm and 55 mm. Figure 6 shows the strain distribution when the measurement surface was set as the upper surface, for delamination lengths of 35 mm and 55 mm. In both figures, the delamination depth is expressed as a percentage of the thickness from the lower surface.

From Figure 5, it was found that the delamination depth reaches a maximum value 1 mm to the left of the delamination tip at all positions. As the depth increases toward the 50% thickness position of the specimen (depth 2.25 mm), the maximum value increases, but from 50% depth to 66.7% depth, the maximum value remains almost unchanged. Additionally, this trend was found to be independent of the delamination length.

Figure 6 shows the compression side, where strain is negative. However, when the delamination depth is close to the sensor (61.1–77.8%), a sharp valley appears compared to the tensile side shown in

(a) Delamination length of 35mm

(b) Delamination length of 55mm

Figure 5: Surface strain distribution on the tensile side at 3-point bending tests with delamination exists at various depth..

(a) Delamination length of 35mm

(b) Delamination length of 55mm

Figure 6: Surface strain distribution on the compressive side at 3-point bending tests with delamination exists at various depth..

Figure 5, indicating that the strain perturbation at the delamination tip differs between the tensile and compression sides. This is because the tensile side layer is subjected to concentrated loads due to the fulcrum, whereas the compressive side receives loads through the peel surface. When measuring the compressive side, similar to the tensile side, the depth of the peel from the sensor surface increases as the delamination depth progresses toward the center, causing the valley depth of the strain peak to increase, but decreases as the peel moves away from the center.

Based on the above results, it was found that determining the delamination depth is difficult using only the peak height measurement of one side, except when the delamination depth is near the sensor surface. Therefore, it is considered necessary to place sensors on both the upper and lower surfaces to achieve accurate delamination depth determination. Rayleigh scattering-type distribution sensors can measure a very long range with a single sensor, so it is believed that simultaneous measurement of both upper and lower surfaces through appropriate sensor placement enables the identification of depth positions.

3.3 Relationship between strain perturbation peak and depth-wise position

It has been clarified that the peak height of strain is influenced by the depth position. Therefore, to quantitatively clarify this relationship, the strain distribution on the surface of a laminated plate without delamination was used as a reference, and the strain distribution in the presence of delamination was subtracted to obtain the perturbation distribution caused by delamination. The normalized distribution of the perturbation relative to the load point strain is shown in Figure 7. Additionally, to investigate the influence of plate thickness, FEM analysis was also performed for a plate thickness of 9 mm.

From the figure, it can be seen that in both thicknesses, when the delamination is inserted at a depth of 33.3% from the measurement surface, a clear valley is observed. On the other hand, as the delamination moves away from the measurement surface, only peaks appear. It was found that up to a

Figure 7: Perturbation of strain by delamination at 3-point bending tests.

Figure 8: Relationship between normalized perturbation peak caused by delamination at 3-point bending tests for specimens of 4.5- and 9-mm thicknesses.

depth of 50%, the size of the peaks increases monotonically with the depth of the delamination. This trend is similar regardless of thickness, indicating that the size of the peaks is a useful feature for estimating depth. On the other hand, it was also found that as the thickness increases, the peak shapes of the peaks and valleys become less pronounced. Therefore, it was found that although plate thickness affects the distribution of strain perturbations caused by delamination, it is likely possible to detect the depth from the perturbation peak within the range from the measurement surface to the central thickness.

Figure 8 shows the relationship between the height of the disturbance peak and the delamination depth position normalized by plate thickness for plate thicknesses of 4.5 mm and 9 mm, respectively. From the figure, it can be seen that in the case of a thickness of 9 mm, the depth increases monotonically up to 50%, and the peak value decreases monotonically beyond 50%. However, in the case of 4.5 mm, it can be seen that the depth decreases once at 33.3%. This is likely due to stress concentration at the support point influencing the perturbation distribution.

In summary, regardless of plate thickness, it was found that the depth of delamination can be estimated from the height of the perturbation peak. Additionally, when the delamination depth is close to the sensor surface, the height of the perturbation valley is a better indicator.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we investigated the effects of delamination depth and plate thickness on the detection of interlaminar delamination in CFRP using a Rayleigh scattering-type distribution sensor. Experimental and FEM analysis results showed good agreement, demonstrating that the spatial resolution and accuracy of the sensor are sufficient for detecting the leading edge position of interlaminar delamination. Furthermore, the analysis results indicated that the position of the delamination depth is strongly correlated with the normalized strain peak. This correlation showed a similar trend even when the plate thickness varied. However, since the peak height is maximum near the center of the specimen, it is necessary to determine whether the delamination depth is close to the sensor surface. However, when the delamination depth is near the sensor surface, a characteristic valley is observed, making identification easy.

Therefore, by using this sensor on both the upper and lower surfaces, it was found that it is possible to simultaneously determine the position and depth of the interlaminar delamination tip.

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